

SCIENCE IN THE CLASSROOM, FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD AND PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

III – THE DYNAMICS OF KNOWLEDGE

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ABSTRACT

In the two preceding articles, we defined knowledge as the representation of the world within the mind. In this paper, we examine the processes through which such representation is constructed and sustained. The discussion is grounded in Piaget's concept of *schema*, which in his genetic epistemology constitutes the basic unit of knowledge. We argue that these schemas emerge from the relationship between concepts stored in Quiroga's neurons, activated through words (signifiers), in accordance with Saussure's theory of evocation. In this framework, language can be conceived as the set of rules that determine how conceptual neurons are successively activated and interconnected, following grammatical structures and giving rise to thought as the manipulation of schemas. Programming language would thus correspond to Fodor's (1975) notion of *mentalese*, conceived around Chomsky's universal grammar.

To describe these processes, we draw on logical and conditional operators common to programming languages, particularly conjunction (**AND**), disjunction (**OR**), and the conditional (**IF–THEN**). In this view, the mental representation of the world occurs through schemas or networks of schemas that articulate the rules governing reality. Piagetian mechanisms of assimilation—understood as the reinforcement of confidence in a given representation—and of disequilibrium and accommodation—as the engine for replacing one representation with a more accurate one—are introduced as explanatory tools.

Finally, Kuhn's theory is presented to illustrate how the problem of increasing precision in scientific representations is resolved within scientific communities. The process, we argue, is strikingly analogous to Piaget's account of individual cognitive development. This parallel suggests that both reflect a —possibly unique— mechanism of knowledge improvement: the Hegelian dialectic.

Keywords: genetic epistemology, cognitive schemas, language and thought, assimilation and accommodation, paradigm shift.

1. INTRODUCTION

We shall begin this work where we left off with the model of the human being presented in previous papers: the Kantian model. According to this conception, the human being is a subject endowed with a mind in which to represent the external world, and with senses through which information from that world is obtained. This information is processed in accordance with a set of categories suited to carrying out such representation.

This approach bears a notable resemblance to the model of an artificial intelligence agent, composed of sensors that collect information from the environment, a knowledge base that organizes and processes such information, and actuators that enable interaction with the environment.

Artificial intelligence Agent

The use of the agent metaphor proves useful in this study, as it allows us to distinguish two forms of increasing a person's cognitive capacity. The first originates in the growth of knowledge acquired through learning and experience, which translates into a greater quantity of data available to represent the environment, as well as the availability of more efficient algorithms for signal processing and logical operations, also incorporated through learning.

The second corresponds to hardware improvement—that is, the expansion of available memory, computational capacity, and so forth—in line with the developmental stages described by Piaget. This distinction makes it possible to analyze both aspects separately, each equally important for enhancing intelligence, understood as a means of adaptation... not through the modification of organs, but through the construction of structures of thought (Piaget, 1967, p. 18).

In this paper, we will examine how our AI agent becomes increasingly intelligent without modifying its hardware, and we will study how these two fundamental operations take place: the acquisition of knowledge from information and, conversely, the acquisition of new information from stored knowledge. These operations form the foundation of scientific knowledge and, ultimately, the outcome of the instinct or innate drive we call curiosity. The emergence of curiosity was most likely a natural result of evolution: those who possessed greater curiosity acquired more knowledge—a superior form of adaptation to the environment—and consequently, greater chances of survival.

2. THE SCHEME, ATOM OF KNOWLEDGE

Jean Piaget defined the scheme as the basic unit of cognitive activity: a fundamental structure of thought that allows experience to be organized and reality to be given meaning (Piaget, 1936/1977; Piaget, 1967/2001). In this sense, the scheme is the fundamental unit of knowledge (not of information!), the foundation upon which progressively more complex cognitive structures are developed (Flavell, 1963; Inhelder & Piaget, 1955/2000).

A Piagetian scheme consists of two parts:

1. The subject's action upon the world.
2. The world's response to that action.

Let us imagine, for clarity, that a girl of about eighteen months experiments with different objects:

- She pushes a chair and it moves.
- She pushes a wall and it does not move.
- She pushes her dog and the dog pushes back.
- She pushes a ball and it rolls.

She continues acting upon the world and observing its reactions, and she realizes that certain objects roll when pushed:

- Ball → rolls.
- Bottle → rolls.
- Orange → rolls.
- Marble → rolls.

2.1. LOGICAL INDUCTIONS

Each of these observations constitutes a kind of unit of information (not of knowledge!) that refers to a single fact with fixed and concrete elements. Storing in memory all the concrete cases obtained from the world would require infinite capacity, which human beings do not possess. To solve this problem, the mind resorts to the mechanism of conceptualization that we already know. Thus, the girl recognizes that all the objects that roll are round (they share the common feature of roundness) and extracts a general rule formulated as a logical implication: if this holds (roundness), then that occurs (rolling). This is one of Kant's categories discussed earlier—the principle of causality—which Chomsky included as a characteristic of universal grammar used to analyze and describe reality:

IF (I push a round object) THEN (it rolls).

Here occurs the crucial step from information (particular schemes or instances of propositions referring to concrete objects) to knowledge (a general scheme or universal statement referring to all round objects in the world). This process is not simple and deserves careful analysis. In it we can distinguish several mental actions. The first is abstraction, which we already know: identifying the common property, roundness, in the set of rolling objects. The second is induction: generalizing from a few observed cases to the infinite round objects that may exist, about which we have not experimented.

The result can be expressed in symbolic language:

IF (X is round), THEN (X rolls).

Here, *X* is represented in the brain by a Quiroga neuron group that activates when we think of or see something round.

This step implies the human capacity to operate with symbols. The symbol *X*, which in ordinary language corresponds to the word *round*, is the signifier in Saussure's sense (1916/2007). When heard by the child, it activates in her brain the neural networks associated with the concept, which is equivalent to evoking its meaning (Quiroga, 2005, 2017).

As we see, symbols (or words) can be used in a structure that relates them. The principle of causality links roundness with rolling. This relation between concepts forms a sentence—the essence of a language. And the way in which concepts are related is what we call grammar (Chomsky, 1965).

Logical connectors and universal grammar

The girl in our example soon realizes that round objects do not roll on their own. They need someone to push them. As a result, she adds one more condition to her scheme:

IF (X is round), THEN (X rolls)

becomes:

IF {(X is round) AND (I push it)} THEN (X rolls).

We see that in addition to the conditional IF... THEN, a logical connector appears: the conjunction *AND*, which allows the introduction of multiple causes that must be satisfied simultaneously in the same causal relation. This new scheme contains more knowledge about the world than the simpler previous one.

It is very useful to represent this sentence as a path that moves from left to right and is interrupted by two successive barriers, corresponding to the conditions indicated in parentheses:

IF {(X is round) AND (I push it)} THEN (X rolls).

If a condition is satisfied, the barrier opens and allows the path to continue; if it is not satisfied, it remains closed and prevents further progress. Only when both barriers open is it possible to reach the end of the path, which is equivalent to the global condition of the sentence being fulfilled.

But the girl continues experimenting, acting upon the world, and observes that round objects also roll, even without being pushed, if they are on a slope. By introducing this new condition, the Piagetian scheme now becomes:

IF {(X is round) AND {(I push it) OR (it is on a slope)}} THEN (X rolls).

As we can see, the grammatical structure is the same, but now the condition for truth is that one of the two conditions is satisfied—being pushed or being on a slope—alternatively or simultaneously.

It is quite simple to construct an electrical circuit with AND and OR logic gates that behaves exactly like this scheme. One would only need an AND gate combining the inputs *round* and *push*, whose output is connected to an OR gate along with the input *slope*. The final output would activate the state *roll*.

In fact, computers work this way: every complex operation they perform can ultimately be reduced to combinations of elementary logic gates such as AND and OR. The same occurs with the knowledge base of an artificial intelligence agent, which organizes its inferences from conditional rules of the type IF... THEN and complementary logical connectors.

These logic gates are nothing more than a simplified artificial model of what neurons do in the brain: integrating multiple synaptic inputs, weighting them, and firing a response only when a certain activation threshold is exceeded.

2.2. LOGICAL DEDUCTIONS

Once the general law or universal statement has been constructed, thought can follow the reverse path, moving from the general to the particular—that is, the process of deduction. Suppose the child has assimilated the universal statement:

IF (X is round) AND {(I push it) OR (it is on a slope)} THEN (X rolls).

When confronted with an unknown object, such as an egg, she can directly apply this same scheme (as stored knowledge) to predict its behavior:

IF (the egg is round) THEN (it will roll).

Since the child recognizes the property of roundness in the egg, she immediately deduces that it will roll, obtaining particular information from general knowledge.

The ability to apply general rules to particular cases allows the chaining of statements in a way similar to Aristotelian logic. Consider the following reasoning:

1. Everything that is round rolls.
2. The egg is round.
3. Therefore, the egg rolls.

This scheme reproduces the model of the Aristotelian categorical syllogism—in this case, of the *Darii* type—in which, from a major premise (1, general law, A) and a minor premise (2, particular statement, I), a particular conclusion (I) is deduced (Aristotle, 2007).

3. THINKING AS SYMBOLIC ACTIVATION

In *La psychologie de l'intelligence* (1947) and *Biologie et connaissance* (1967), Piaget pointed out that thinking consists of operating on schemes—combining them, coordinating them, or transforming them. We can therefore define thought as a process in which the brain internally “pronounces” words that, when evoked, activate the

neuronal groups corresponding to the concepts they represent. Each word functions as a symbolic trigger: its mere mental articulation activates the neural network that stores the associated concept.

In this way, thinking becomes a sequence of symbolic activations that evoke, one after another, representations of objects, properties, or relations. Thus, when thinking the sentence *the ball rolls*, the neuronal groups *ball* and *roll* are activated in the order determined by the conditional structure, reproducing in the mind the action described as if we were actually seeing it. If each neuron had a light that turned on when activated, a sentence would appear as a series of neurons lighting up sequentially as the words that evoke them are pronounced. And in our imagination, we would see the scene we are describing in words.

The relations between Piagetian schemes occur, as we have seen, according to fixed rules that can be identified with those of the universal grammar proposed by Chomsky. Building on this idea, Jerry Fodor argued that the existence of a grammar necessarily implies the existence of an underlying language, a language of the brain that can be translated into any spoken language, which he called *mentalese* (Fodor, 1975).

Chomsky argues that all human languages share a set of basic structural principles—the universal grammar—including conjunction, disjunction, and conditionality (Chomsky, 1965/2014; 1986).

- Spanish: *y, o, si*
- English: *and, or, if*
- French: *et, ou, si*
- Japanese: *matawa* (or), *-tara* (if)

Analogous to humans, artificial intelligence agents operate with an internal programming language in which conditional rules of the form IF ... THEN, together with logical connectors AND and OR, structure their processes of inference and action. Just as *mentalese* provides humans with an underlying grammar for thinking and reasoning, programming languages provide AI with the ability to process information, generate knowledge, and plan actions. In this sense, the parallelism is clear: *mentalese* can be considered the “programming language” of the human mind—the language of thought.

4. GROWTH OF KNOWLEDGE THROUGH ASSIMILATION

We have seen that the knowledge we construct as a representation of the real world is composed of *schemes*. This knowledge can increase in two ways: either because the portion of the represented world expands, or because the representation becomes deeper, more detailed, or more precise. When this increase occurs while maintaining the same ontology—that is, the same scenario in which the concepts and observational

processes are situated—the mechanism is called assimilation. Below, we examine how different authors have conceived this process of increasing knowledge.

In his theory of cognitive development, Piaget defines assimilation as the process by which an individual incorporates new observations or experimental results that are consistent with a previously established knowledge scheme, thereby reinforcing it (Piaget, 1967/2001).

An example of this process can be observed in the following scheme: every 28 days a new moon occurs. By repeatedly verifying that the new moon appears every 28 days, the subject assimilates this regularity as a general law. No new knowledge is generated, but there is an increase in the certainty that the knowledge is true.

David Ausubel also used the term assimilation to refer to a process of increasing knowledge, although in his case it denotes a mechanism different from Piaget's and, in our opinion, of greater relevance in the educational field.

In the theory of meaningful learning (Ausubel, 1968/2002), assimilation is understood as the process by which new information is integrated into an already existing cognitive structure, thanks to the mediation of inclusive or subsuming concepts.

An example of this concept of assimilation is that of a student who already knows the concept of mammal: when told that dolphins are mammals, the student simply transfers their characteristics to the new group, extending to dolphins the features that define mammals, such as breathing through lungs.

The key to Ausubel's approach lies in the fact that assimilation fulfills a synthesizing function: it allows two concepts to be united into one, reducing the complexity of the representation of the world through meaningful connections between the new and the already understood. Hence his famous statement: "*The most important single factor influencing learning is what the learner already knows. Ascertain this and teach accordingly*" (Ausubel, 1968, p. vi).

As we can see, assimilation is not truly an increase in our knowledge of the world, but rather an increase in the certainty that the knowledge we already possess is true.

From a different perspective, Lev Vygotsky (1934/1995) understands assimilation as an essentially social and cultural process. For Vygotsky, assimilation is the process by which individuals in a society acquire or assimilate the cultural knowledge and values of that society, which in turn is the mechanism through which society assimilates the individuals who compose it.

5. INCREASE OF KNOWLEDGE THROUGH *DISEQUILIBRIUM* AND *ACCOMMODATION: ONLY FROM ERRORS DO WE LEARN*

A central axis in Piaget's work is the study of the emergence of new knowledge through the process of disequilibrium and accommodation (Piaget, 1970, 1975).

When existing schemes prove insufficient to account for new experimental results or observations, the human experiences cognitive *disequilibrium* that forces him to modify or reorganize prior structures. The outcome of this process is **accommodation**—that is, the creation of a new scheme that replaces, transforms, or even invalidates the previous one.

Piaget had already introduced the concepts of assimilation and accommodation in his early works—*The Language and Thought of the Child* (1923) and *The Construction of Reality in the Child* (1937)—applying them to describe how young children adapt their schemes to experience.

A clear example is observed in the innate action of sucking: when the infant applies it to the mother's breast, they obtain food, but when applying it to other objects they do not. This is probably the first scheme that the infant constructs:

- “I suck a finger → I do not obtain food.”
- “I suck a hand → I do not obtain food.”
- “I suck a pacifier → I do not obtain food.”

From these experiences, the child continues to act upon the external world and gradually constructs a more general scheme, which could be expressed in our symbolic language as follows:

IF {(I suck X) AND (X is not the breast)} THEN (I do not obtain food).

The infant continues to apply the action of sucking in different situations and objects, progressively reinforcing the scheme through a process of assimilation.

After some time, the mother loses the ability to feed her baby, who desperately experiences the fact of not obtaining food despite sucking the breast. Consequently, the mother decides to feed the child with bottles and brings the bottle's teat to the baby's mouth. The child sucks with the expectation, according to the previous scheme, that no food will be obtained. However, to his surprise, this time food is indeed obtained. In this case, the previous scheme:

IF {(I suck X) AND (X is not the breast)} THEN (I do not obtain food).

is refuted, since for $X = \text{bottle}$ an exception arises. The infant undergoes a state of unease, of cognitive disequilibrium, a kind of uncertainty akin to being in an unfamiliar environment, not knowing how things behave.

According to Piaget, the child's reaction—whether innate or acquired, depending on interpretation—is to modify the previous scheme, which has proven inaccurate, in order to accommodate it to the new information. The result is the formulation of a new scheme and the discarding of the earlier one:

IF {(I suck X) AND (X is not the bottle)} THEN (I do not obtain food).

where the refutation of the previous scheme is implicit.

Thus, the infant increases his knowledge of the world through the destruction of the previous scheme and the construction of a new one, adapted to experience. This process of *disequilibrium–accommodation* is used throughout life and is equivalent, if not identical, to the mechanism that drives science forward.

A particularly clear example is the case of children's beliefs in the Three Wise Men, Santa Claus, or the Tooth Fairy. During the preoperational stage (approximately between ages 4 and 7), children accept these figures as real and attribute to them the magical ability to bring gifts or collect teeth, consistent with animistic thought and the tendency to explain phenomena through supernatural agents described by Piaget (1936/1977).

However, as cognitive development progresses, contradictions with direct experience arise—store labels on gifts, accidental discoveries of parents' preparations—that cause disequilibrium in the prior scheme. This disequilibrium leads to accommodation: the child comes to understand that it is the parents who carry out these actions.

6. A NEW CONCEPT IN THE HISTORY OF SCIENCE: THE PARADIGM

When a child discovers that the Tooth Fairy or Santa Claus do not exist, it is not only his knowledge that changes but also his way of understanding reality and the nature of the laws that govern it. Thomas Kuhn, in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* (1962/2004), uses the term *paradigm* to refer to such a change, defining it as the set of beliefs, values, techniques, and ontological and epistemological assumptions shared by members of a scientific community. Yet Kuhn himself (1970) acknowledges the ambiguity of the term's usage and later, in the 1969 *Postscript*, attempts to clarify his definition—although, in our view, not entirely successfully.

Defining a concept is never an easy task. A classic example is Plato, who defined the human being as a featherless biped. Diogenes the Cynic, to highlight the limits of that definition, brought a plucked chicken into the Academy and declared: "Here is a man."

In order to shape or refine the idea of a paradigm, let us consider some examples from different fields, so that the concept gradually takes form in our minds.

- In **education**, a paradigm defines what it means to learn: in the behaviorist paradigm, learning consists of establishing stimulus-response associations reinforced by rewards or punishments; in the constructivist paradigm, by contrast, learning means that the student actively constructs knowledge from prior experiences and interaction with the environment.
- In **politics**, a paradigm determines the source of legitimacy of power: in the absolutist paradigm, the king rules by divine will, while in the Enlightenment's democratic paradigm, sovereignty resides in the will of the citizens.
- In **social organization**, paradigms establish hierarchies and roles: in the patriarchal paradigm of classical Greece, men were considered superior to women, as reflected in the phrase: "I thank the gods for having been born Greek and not barbarian, man and not woman, free and not slave, but above all for having been born in the age of Socrates"; in contrast, the contemporary feminist paradigm recognizes equal rights and dignity for men and women.
- In the **history of knowledge**, paradigms shape the way reality is explained: in the magical paradigm, natural phenomena were attributed to supernatural forces that could be influenced by ritual dances; in the pre-scientific paradigm, explanation relied on the authority of philosophers rather than experimental observation, as when Aristotle claimed that bodies fell because they sought their "natural place"; in the scientific paradigm, by contrast, nature is studied through observation, hypothesis formulation, and experimental verification, as demonstrated by Einstein's theory of relativity confirmed by astronomical observations.

Thus, by tracing examples from education, politics, social organization, and science, we see that a paradigm is not a mere theory but a comprehensive framework of representation: a set of beliefs, values, and practices that defines what counts as valid knowledge and how reality is interpreted in a given time and place. The concept of paradigm is equally important in relation to the social values that structure coexistence, such as issues of race, gender, or social class.

7. KUHN OR GENETIC EPISTEMOLOGY APPLIED TO HUMAN SOCIETIES

In his study of the advancement of knowledge, Kuhn essentially replaces Piaget's child by the scientific community.

While Piaget analyzes the evolution of individual cognitive schemes in childhood, Kuhn describes the transformation of paradigms shared by scientific communities. The analogy can be illustrated with an image: Piaget studies the mental trajectory of an ant exploring and representing its environment; Kuhn studies the behavior of the entire anthill, its internal rules, forms of organization, and collective patterns of adaptation.

In this parallel, Kuhn begins with a scientific community holding a particular paradigm and body of knowledge that define what he calls *normal science*. His example is the early sixteenth century, with Ptolemaic geocentrism and Galen's anatomy. At this stage

of normal science, the process of Piagetian assimilation translates into the incorporation of new knowledge within the prevailing schemes, without the need to modify the paradigm.

However, when persistent anomalies arise that do not fit within the theoretical framework of normal science—such as inaccuracies in astronomical calculations, the appearance of comets, Galileo’s observations of Jupiter’s satellites or the phases of Venus, and errors in Galen’s anatomical descriptions—a state of crisis emerges in the scientific community. This is analogous to the cognitive disequilibrium described by Piaget in individuals: accumulated knowledge ceases to suffice, and a space of uncertainty opens.

Eventually, the scientific community accommodates itself to the new facts and observations, concretized in the landmark publications of 1543: Copernicus’s *De revolutionibus orbium coelestium* and Vesalius’s *De humani corporis fabrica*. These works established a new *paradigm* so different from the previous one that Kuhn defines the change as a *scientific revolution*, corresponding to the process of Piagetian accommodation: the old paradigm is replaced by a new, broader, and more powerful one, giving rise to what Kuhn calls *new science*, which reorganizes the understanding of the world and redefines the problems to be investigated in the future.

Thus, the scientific community, conceived as a super-organism of knowledge, produces, preserves, transforms, and transmits knowledge over time, through practices, institutions, and generations (Kuhn, 1962; Latour & Woolgar, 1979).

These changes—whether accommodation in individuals or new science in scientific communities—are always preceded by a certain resistance. During this period, both children and scientists attempt to interpret novel phenomena using outdated conceptual frameworks, striving to fit the unprecedented into previous structures that are no longer adequate.

This dynamic of resistance, common both in Kuhn’s epistemology and in Piaget’s developmental psychology, was starkly described by Max Planck in the context of science, when he declared that “a new scientific truth does not triumph by convincing its opponents and making them see the light, but rather because its opponents eventually die, and a new generation grows up familiar with it” (Planck, 1949, p. 33). This statement, known as Planck’s principle, underscores that the progress of knowledge does not necessarily depend on rational persuasion, but on generational replacement that enables the consolidation of new cognitive or paradigmatic structures.

The curious correlation between the history of humanity and the development of human beings

If we take the scientific paradigms through which science has advanced as a measure of the progress of societies throughout history, and compare them with the stages of Piagetian cognitive development in children, we find that both processes reveal striking similarities.

Paradigms of light and their correspondence with Piaget's stages

<u>Paradigm (Kuhn)</u>	<u>Cognitive stage (Piaget)</u>	<u>Didactic description</u>
Corpuscular (From Classical Greece to Newton, 1704)	Preoperational thought (2–7 years)	Intuitive explanation: light consists of particles that travel in straight lines. Appropriate to everyday experience and to concrete thought.
Wave (Huygens, Young, Fresnel, 1678–1821)	Concrete operations (7–11 years)	Use of analogies (waves in water) to understand phenomena such as interference and diffraction. Development of logical causality.
Quantum (Einstein, 1905)	Formal operations (12+ years)	Light behaves as a wave or as a particle depending on the experiment. Requires abstract reasoning and the management of conceptual dualities.

The correlation between the stages of cognitive development with increasing age and the succession of scientific paradigms throughout history must have a deeper underlying explanation. In our view, this suggests that software—knowledge—is ultimately equivalent to hardware, that is, to the power of logical–mathematical processing.

This becomes evident if we compare two levels of analysis. On the one hand, Piaget's theory of cognitive development can be related to our AI agent model applied to the individual. On the other hand, Kuhn's model of scientific paradigms can be applied to society, which we may conceive as a kind of human anthill organized around knowledge.

When scientific discoveries in a society give rise to new technologies, the society adapts by creating new specialized professions to manage this emerging knowledge. As a result, its problem-solving capacity expands, enabling the construction of new machines and the achievement of further discoveries. In the anthill analogy, the cognitive capacity of society increases.

Thus, as children's cognitive capacities develop, the scientific paradigms accessible to them also evolve—just as societies, through historical progression, gain access to increasingly advanced paradigms. In this way, the development of knowledge in society mirrors the stages of cognitive development in children, which explains the correlation we have emphasized.

8. CONCLUSION

Within this framework, the history of science can be understood as a form of social genetic psychology, in which scientific communities, like individuals, undergo stages of cognitive development through processes of assimilation, disequilibrium, and accommodation described by Piaget and Kuhn (Kuhn, 1962/2012; Piaget, 1975). Following this analogy, science education should be conceived as a process of conceptual reconstruction, guiding students from their prior schemes—often intuitive or pre-scientific—toward more abstract, complex, and formalized models (Driver, Guesne, & Tiberghien, 1985).

It could be objected that the development of individuals is not strictly comparable to that of societies, since in the early stages of education cognitive capacity does not remain constant, but evolves with age and neurological development (Inhelder & Piaget, 1958; Case, 1985). However, this variation in human *hardware* can be paralleled with the instrumental advances that drive the development of science: telescopes, microscopes, X-rays, computers, CT scans, PET, MRI, or ultrasound, all of which expand the possibilities of observation, accumulation, and transformation of knowledge.

Although Piaget and Kuhn worked in different fields—the psychology of development and the philosophy of science—their theories present clear points of convergence. For Piaget (1970, 1975), cognitive development does not progress in a linear or cumulative way, but through successive reorganizations triggered by processes of assimilation, disequilibrium, and accommodation. Similarly, Kuhn (1962/2012) showed that scientific progress does not follow a simple accumulation of data either, but is structured in periods of normal science, interrupted by crises that open the way to paradigm shifts. In both cases, crisis—whether cognitive or scientific—constitutes the driving force behind the construction of new, more powerful, and more general structures.

Piaget spoke of cognitive structures that balance and reorganize in childhood; Kuhn, for his part, described conceptual structures that delimit the practice of a scientific community. Kuhn himself acknowledged the influence of genetic epistemology on his work, following the dialogues he held with Piaget at the International Center for Genetic Epistemology in Geneva during the 1960s, where they coincided. Knowledge progresses more through structural reorganizations than through mere accumulation.

Ultimately, the works of Piaget and Kuhn intersect and enrich one another: Piaget provides the psychological basis for understanding how individuals construct and transform their schemes, while Kuhn offers the historical basis for analyzing how scientific communities modify their paradigms. Taken together, both show that the progress of knowledge, both individual and collective, is better explained as a process of structural reorganization driven by the tension between equilibrium and disequilibrium, rather than as a linear accumulation of data.

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